

PSYCHOLOGICAL STRUCTURE OF SPEECH DISORDERS IN GENERAL UNDERDEVELOPMENT OF SPEECH IN PRESCHOOL AGE

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In accordance with the theoretical concepts of Russian psychology, speech is the most important mental function of a person - a universal means of communication, thinking, and organizing actions. Many studies have established that all mental processes are mediated by speech. Deviations in the development of speech negatively affect the mental development of the child, make it difficult to communicate with others, delay the formation of cognitive processes and, consequently, prevent the formation of a full-fledged personality. The development of the child's personality and further education at school depends on the timeliness and effectiveness of correctional work.

Speech disorders and psychological characteristics of children with speech disorders are studied by speech pedagogy and speech psychology as branches of special pedagogy and special psychology. Speech disorders determine the peculiarities of cognitive activity and the personal sphere of the child. In order to carry out effective logopedic correction work to overcome psychorechological and personality-communicative disorders in children with general speech underdevelopment, it is advisable to use comprehensive psychological and pedagogical support.

Comprehensive psychological and pedagogical support is defined as a joint professional activity of specialists of a preschool educational institution, which is aimed at creating pedagogical and socio-psychological conditions for the successful learning and development of this contingent of children, regardless of their level of cognitive abilities and the level of speech development. The success of joint correctional and pedagogical work with children with severe speech disorders largely depends on the properly organized interaction of a speech therapist, educators, medical workers, a psychologist, a music director, physical education and visual activity teachers, a social pedagogue and parents. Each of the teachers, solving their tasks defined by educational programs and regulations on preschool educational institutions, should take part in the formation and consolidation of correct speech skills and abilities in children, in the development of the sensorimotor sphere, higher mental functions and health promotion.

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Speech pedagogy is engaged in the study of speech disorders and the development of scientifically based methods and techniques for their prevention, detection and elimination by means of special training and education. She studies the causes, mechanisms, symptoms, course, structure of speech disorders. The subject of speech pedagogy as a scientific discipline

is speech disorders and the process of education and upbringing of persons with speech disorders.

Modern research in the field of special pedagogy and psychology, speech therapy practice, as well as qualitative changes in the contingent of special educational institutions for children with general speech underdevelopment show that speech disorders cannot be considered as an isolated defect. As is known, speech pathology determines the peculiarities of cognitive activity and personality of children with speech disorders, which may have a different psychological structure and depend on the severity of the speech disorder. Particular attention to this issue is caused by the fact that over the past decade theoretical ideas about speech development disorders have changed and the field of activity for speech therapists has expanded. In this regard, the problems of identifying the psychological characteristics of children with speech disorders and determining effective ways to correct them led to the identification of a new branch in special psychology - logopedics.

The theoretical aspect of logopedics is the study of the mental development of children with speech disorders and the development of scientific methods for the prevention, detection and overcoming of deviations in psychophysical and speech development. The theoretical foundations of logopedics are laid in the studies of L.S. Vygotsky, revealing the structure of the defect of abnormal development of a child. The presence of a primary defect, violations of various components of the speech system in the absence of special measures will lead to secondary and tertiary violations: underdevelopment of all sides of speech, limited sensory, temporal and spatial representations, memory and attention deficiencies, insufficient ability to draw conclusions, generalize, establish causal relationships, difficulties in developing communication skills.

The practical aspect of logopedics in the process of logopedic correction work provides for the use of compensatory capabilities of the child for the development of cognitive activity, sensory and motor functions, the formation of the child's personality and the correction of social relations.

Of particular importance for the development of logopedics is the scientific concept of R.E. Levina. The leading position of its concept is a scientifically based systematic approach to the study of speech and mental characteristics of children with severe speech disorders. For the development of logopedics, the significance of this provision of R.E. Levina's concept is relevant in two aspects: diagnostic and correctional.

Modern psychological and pedagogical diagnostics considers the principle of the relationship of speech with other aspects of mental development, developed by R.E. Levina, as one of the most important principles of studying children with speech disorders. The question posed by R.E. Levina about the need to carry out, together with speech therapy work, the correction of the mental characteristics of children with severe speech disorders is the most urgent task in the modern organization of the special education system. Thus, the scientific works of R.E. Levina substantiate the relevance of modern theoretical and practical problems of logopedics, because without knowledge of the psychological characteristics of children with speech disorders, without knowledge of the compensatory capabilities of higher mental functions of the child, it is impossible to create effective logopedic correctional methods of teaching and educating this category of children.

The main objectives of the experimental speech therapy examination of children with general speech underdevelopment are the following:

- to study general and anamnestic information about children, medical and psychological and pedagogical documentation;
- to study the state of speech activity: the level of formation of the phonetic-phonemic and lexical-grammatical side of speech, the state of independent coherent speech and communication skills;
- to study the state of cognitive activity;
- determine the state of motor development;
- to study personal characteristics.

Children cannot reproduce the syllabic structure of the word. Examination of children's sound pronunciation revealed gross violations in the pronunciation of whistling, hissing sounds and sonors. All examined children have violations of the prosodic side of speech: sluggish articulation, fuzzy diction, general blurring of speech. Children's vocabulary is limited. They have difficulties in naming parts and qualitative characteristics of objects, in the selection of generalizing words, concepts. Persistent grammatical disorders were noted in all children of the experimental groups. Children have particular difficulties mastering the skills of coherent speech: a violation of the coherence and consistency of utterance, the absence of common sentences. Thus, the examination of the state of speech activity in all children showed the lack of formation of all sides of the speech system and, as a result, the presence of communicative difficulties.

The study of the state of cognitive activity revealed an insufficient level of formation of mental operations with the relative safety of other mental functions.

The function of visual perception was the most preserved in children with general speech underdevelopment. Minor difficulties were caused by tasks for the study of auditory perception: the reproduction of rhythmic drawings. When studying the state of memory, low indicators of verbal memory were revealed. All the examined children had consistently low indicators of the formation of mental operations and verbal-logical thinking.

When studying constructive activity, it was revealed that the level of formation of fine motor skills in all children corresponds to average indicators. The study of the personal characteristics of children showed gross deviations in the personal and communicative sphere: increased anxiety, a feeling of loneliness, psychological discomfort, low self-esteem.

Thus, the highlighted features of cognitive activity in children with ONR (level III) in combination with systemic speech underdevelopment indicate the presence of a complex psychorechological disorder. Therefore, in logopsychology, the problem of identifying the features of the psychophysical development of children with speech pathology remains relevant to the present time both at the level of theoretical developments of relevant technologies and at the level of their practical implementation.

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